

Preliminary ecological study of plant species of Lokame Natural Forest (Nord Ubangi Province, Democratic Republic of the Congo): A special emphasis on Non-timber Forest Products

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ABSTRACT:

A preliminary ecological study with a special emphasis on Non-timber forest products (NTFPs) was conducted between 2014 and 2015 on both banks of Lokame River in Lokame forest. The results showed that the Lokame natural forest has a very rich and diversified in NTFPs. Data collected over a total area of 2 ha identified 20 families and 25 different plant species producing NTFPs and 914 individuals, of which 39% are food, 38% for different uses, 14% for aphrodisiacs and 9% as medicinal. A comparison of data by region reveals that the left bank region is richer and more diversified than that of the right bank. Fruit is the most used organ (75%) followed by bark (60%) and leaves (50%). The unbarking is the most important collection technique for the entire study area with a frequency of 70%. The unbarking is followed by cutting down, collection, picking-up, thinning-out and uprooting. The collection by unbarking, uprooting and cutting down is destructive, henceforth these methods are not sustainable. The proportions of NTFPs collection are alarming for the conservation of Lokame forest area. It is therefore necessary to: (1) strengthen knowledge on NTFPs and sustainable management techniques associated with their exploitation, (2) develop and implement the NTFP-specific institutional and regulatory framework, (3) carry out economic diagnosis and control of the traceability of NTFP sectors, (4) strengthen institutional and human capacities for the development of the NTFP sector, and last (5) create a conducive environment in order to invest in the NTFP sector. Thus, Lokame natural forest will continue to play its role of biodiversity conservation and sustained production of natural resources.

Keyword: *Non-timber Forest Products, Lokame forest ecosystem, Nord-Ubangi Province.*

INTRODUCTION

The challenge of sustainable forest management that the International Community undertook at the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 requires the definition and implementation of new policies aimed at the sustainable knowledge and use of Non-timber Forest Products (NTFPs). The increasingly important role of NTFPs in economic and social development in our countries fully justifies this approach. A genuine program to promote the use of NTFPs should be developed based on certain international agreements (the Convention on Biological Diversity, the International Commitment on Plant Genetic Resources, etc.) and implemented with the appropriate support of the International community [1, 2].

The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) has an important diversified wealth in NTFPs. These products cover the daily food needs of rural populations and complement those of urban populations. Moreover, because of its importance in the Congolese economy, the wood represents to this day the principal forest product, which is the main focus of forest management action. Nowadays, the forest inventories carried out which focused

exclusively on commercial timber species, for forestry planning purposes, are necessary proof of this. However, in recent years, the government has adopted a policy of sustainable forest management as an ecosystem. Thus, all the biological elements of the forest must be taken into account in its management [3].

Since the immemorial times, the Congolese forest has constituted an important source of income and a large reserve for the satisfaction of various needs, mainly food, for the entire population and especially for the populations living in the forest areas [4-10]. The most exploited NTFPs in forest areas are: food crops (fruits, wild vegetables, tubers, etc.), medicinal plants, mushrooms, honey and plants for various uses (lianas, rattans, Marantaceae leaves, palm leaves, barks, etc.) [11].

Despite the fact that these products have not been evaluated up to date, it can be said that their potentialities are important, given the quantities consumed since times. Besides, the self-consumption of these products by the local populations, these products are largely sold in the urban markets. "Non-Timber Forest Products" (NTFPs) refer to a wide range of products that are found daily in the houses and markets throughout the Congo Basin. In the Republic of Congo, the Forestry Act of 2000 refers to "Accessory forest

products". In DRC, the forest code of 2002 describes NTFPs as "all other forest products such as rattans, barks, roots, leaves, fruits, seeds, resins, gums and medicinal plants". In the present study, NTFPs are non-woody plant products as defined in the DRC Forest Code [12]. In Lokame forest, NTFPs are plant organs including barks, roots, bulbs, tubers, fruits, seeds, flowers, leaves and sap collected by the local population of this forest and used as food, medicine and for various services. It should be noted that public services in general and the forestry administration in particular have no control over their exploitation, use and marketing.

Despite the fact that these products have not been assessed nowadays, it can be affirmed that their potentialities are important, given the quantities consumed since times. Besides the self-consumption of these products by the local populations, a great part of these products is sent to urban markets [1]. Unfortunately, the overexploitation on one hand and the destruction of forests on the other hand contribute to the scarcity of certain products, particularly wild fruits and medicinal plants. However, some products are virtually no longer exploited, henceforth the need of a bioprospecting study. Bioprospecting is an activity that consists of inventorying or assessing the constitutive components of biodiversity important for its conservation and sustainable use while taking into account the expected inventory standards [1].

The present study was conducted with the aim of inventorying NTFPs in the Lokame forest using Congolese forest inventory standards technique developed by SPIAF (Permanent Service of Inventory and Forestry Management) of the Ministry of Environment, Nature Conservation and Tourism (MECNT) of Democratic Republic of the Congo [13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area and population activities

The forest of Lokame is located in Molengo locality, Bogonda grouping, Ngbakolo sector in Businga territory, in the present province of Nord-Ubangi in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Lokame forest is bounded in the north by Lowa River in the North, in the south by Loko Protestant Missionary Station, the Ubangi forest in the East and Molengo village in the West. The soil of Lokame forest is of type sandy-clay and clay-limonite [14]. The relief of Lokame forest consists of the plateau, the hills and the plains. The rainfall is relatively abundant with an annual average greater than 1600 mm and the insolation is low, i.e. 45% of the total tradition of tropical energy and the intensity of direct solar radiation is 25 cal/cm²/minute [15].

In addition, Lokame forest benefits from the climate of the northern region of DRC i.e. the climate is of Equato-guinean type with two seasons according to Koppen classification [16]. The rainy season is between mid-May and mid-November and the dry season is between mid-November to mid-May. The ambient temperature varies between 21 °C and 31 °C while the average daily temperature is 26 °C and the relative humidity is of 87%. Lokame forest is of equatorial evergreen forest type. Following the anthropogenic activities carried out on this forest, the vegetation is successively composed of grasslands and savannahs mixed with grasslands. Lokame forest is crossed over by Lokame River from which it takes its name. However, there are some streams that spring from the Lokame forest namely Lowa, Lili, Awuka, Mbongo and Toto rivers.

In general, crops are the prerogative of farmers who engage themselves in extensive slash-and-burn agriculture on small areas without the use of improved inputs. Generally, agricultural techniques remain ancestral and rudimentary without respect for the agricultural calendar or density. The work is entirely manual

with the use of an exclusively family labor force. Considering the important place they occupy in crops at the provincial level, cassava, maize, rice, plantain and groundnut are the main vegetable products in Lokame forest.

Fishing is customary and artisanal and it is often performed at night and sometimes during the day. As regards the fishing gear used, the fishermen of Lokame river use mainly gillnets, seines, nets, hawks, hooks, racks and sieves. Some fishermen namely women, practice picking ponds and ponds and sometimes water poisoning.

The flotilla consists of wooden canoes propelled by a paddle. As in the North Ubangi Province, breeding is essentially of the traditional type, the animals do not have suitable shelters and are usually left in wandering, receiving neither care nor supplements. The most widespread livestock breeding in Lokame forest is the native, rustic but poor breeding birds associated with African ducks in almost every household.

Method

The methods used in the present study are those of forest inventory that are simple to implement in the field and therefore inexpensive, but ensure a satisfactory reliability of the results. It should be noted that forest inventories are an integral part of the planning process for the sustainable management of forest resources [17]. Despite the rich forest management experience of our country, a reliable quantification of forest resources remains to be fully understood.

This inventory is the key element in the long-term planning of activities on a forest concession and therefore on the management plan. In order to simplify the logistics, these two phases were carried out jointly in the field: an inventory team consisting of a layout team and a team responsible for counting and complementary surveys. The counting operation that immediately follows the counting process in the field consisted of identifying plants and/or animals species producing Non-Timber Forest Products. The pointer and team leader in charge of this statement notes these measures on the inventory record and data were reported on an inventory list record. The reading was carried out systematically until the end of the line. For each plant or animal species producing NTFP counted, the local name, trade name, scientific name, organ used, use of the organ, average quantity collected per day (per week or per month). Possibly, the means or technique of collection and current trends or prospects.

Species not identifiable botanically were pointed as "unknown", samples were collected and sent to the Herbarium of Faculty of Science, University of Kisangani for appropriate identification.

Data collected during the inventory operations were then analyzed and these analyzes concerned the structural parameters. Structural parameters include structural attributes and structural complexity. Thus, the structural complexity corresponds to the indices of diversity and similarity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inventory carried out in two concessions in the forest of Lokame showed, after interviews and field observations that the great wealth and the floristic diversity of the left and right banks of Lokame River crossing Lokame forest equally. After the investigation, we identified 914 plant species divided into 20 families and 25 different plant species producing NTFPs.

Ayous (*Triplochiton scleroxylon*) is the most frequent species found in Lokame forest (8.20%) followed by Marantaceae (7.65%), *Musanga cecropioides* (6.89%), *Fagara* (6.67%) and *Alstonia boonei* (6.45%). Marantaceae are the most abundant species followed by *Triplochiton scleroxylon* and *Gnetum* although this one is less frequent than *Musanga cecropioides*. The most common trees found belong to *Sterculiaceae*, *Marantaceae*,

Moraceae, *Rutaceae* and *Apocynaceae* families. Regarding lianas, *Maranthocloa*, *Piper guineensis*, *Combretum racemosum* and *Dioscorea spp* are the most common species.

Shrubs form the least biological type found in this forest and only *Morinda morindoides* and *Gnetum spp* are the most encountered species. It should be noted that all the 25 species identified are

common to both zones with a tendency to decrease their number when we go from the left bank to the right bank of Lokame forest. Therefore, this shows that the floristic similarity between both areas is 100%. The number and the frequency of trees found in Lokame forest is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Number and frequency of trees found in both banks of Lokame River located in Lokame forest

Family	Plant species			Sites			
				Left bank	Right bank	Total area	
	Scientific name	Common names	Life form	N	N	N	%
Arecaceae	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i> Jacq.	Palmier à huile	Tree	0	1	1	0.10
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i> (Willd. ex A.Juss.) Müll.Arg.	Hévéa	Tree	0	3	3	0.32
Dioscoreaceae	<i>Dioscorea spp</i>	Ignames sauvages	Liana	1	8	9	0.98
Piperaceae	<i>Piper guineensis</i> Schumach. & Thonn.	Poivron/pili-pili	Liana	7	2	9	0.98
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Macaranga spinosa</i> Müll.Arg.	Nguba ya Zamba	Tree	12	0	12	1.31
Rubiaceae	<i>Morinda morindoides</i> (Baker) Milne-Redh.	Kongo bololo	Tree	13	7	20	2.18
Leguminosae	<i>Scorodophloeus zenkeri</i> Harms	Kanga moyibi	Tree	12	8	20	2.18
Malvaceae	<i>Funtumia elastica</i> (Preuss) Stapf	Ndembo	Tree	12	11	23	2.51
Arecaceae	<i>Raphia spp</i>	Ndele	Tree	17	11	28	3.06
Malvaceae	<i>Cola nitida</i> (Vent.) Schott & Endl.	Colatier	Tree	25	4	29	3.17
Gnetaceae	<i>Gnetum spp</i>	Fumbwa	Liana	15	15	30	3.28
Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus larinicus</i> Burch	Moyibi	Herb	22	8	30	3.28
Combretaceae	<i>Combretum racemosum</i> P.Beauv.	Mukala	Liana	20	12	32	3.50
Leguminosae	<i>Bobgunnia fistuloides</i> (Harms) J.H.Kirkbr. & Wiersema	Mibalisambo/Mbulongo	Shrub	35	0	35	3.82
Malvaceae	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Gbukulu/Fromager	Tree	32	12	44	4.81
Moraceae	<i>Milicia excelsa</i> (Welw.) C.C.Berg	Mbangi/Iroko	Tree	32	15	47	5.14
Meliaceae	<i>Entandrophragma cylindricum</i> (Sprague) Sprague	Sapelli	Tree	35	15	50	5.47
Burseraceae	<i>Dacryodes edulis</i> (G.Don) H.J.Lam	Safoutier/Bosau	Tree	35	18	53	5.79
Annonaceae	<i>Anonidium mannii</i> (Oliv.) Engl. & Diels	Corossolier/mopombi	Tree	37	18	55	6.01
Zingiberaceae	<i>Afromomum spp</i>	Tondolo	Herb	38	18	56	6.12
Apocynaceae	<i>Alstonia boonei</i> De Wild.	Gugia	Tree	42	17	59	6.45
Rutaceae	<i>Fagara spp</i>	-	Tree	43	18	61	6.67
Urticaceae	<i>Musanga cecropioides</i> R.Br. ex Tedlie	Kombokombo, nvonvo	Tree	3	60	63	6.89
Marantaceae	<i>Marantochloa spp</i>	-	Herb	46	24	70	7.65
Malvaceae	<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i> K.Schum.	Ayous/Gbadogbado	Tree	50	25	75	8.20

The floristic and structural composition of Lokame forest on the left and right banks is much diversified, as is the case in all the tropical forests throughout the world. This diversity is reflected not only in their specific richness but also in their biological types. Field observations allowed noting that Lokame forest has a vertical structure composed of 3 strata according to biological types. A very dense lower stratum composed of grasses and lianas, a medium stratum consisting of shrubs and finally a superior stratum mainly consisting of *Triplochiton scleroxylon* feet and trees. NTFP-producing species are recruited among these different biological types. This gives a secondary forest structure to the *Triplochiton scleroxylon* called *Gbadogbado* by the local communities.

Whatever the area, the tree constitutes the majority element in the forest followed by grasses, lianas and finally shrubs. However, there is a gradual diminution of trees and vines while going from the left to the right bank. This could be explained by the fact that the forest on the left bank lies close to the natural forest where the anthropogenic activity is almost reduced, unlike the right bank where its ecosystems are under pressure from the population of the

neighboring village.

The presence of lianas is the one of the characteristics of the primal forest and we observed that there are a large number of lianas on the left bank of Lokame River which proves that there is a gradient of ecological stability in this zone due to the lack of anthropogenic activities. The distribution of the number of species inventoried by biological type in all three zones (left bank and right bank) is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of species according to biological types
 In total, 914 individuals were inventoried, divided into 4 plant types (of which the trees are the most represented), subdivided into 25 plant species and 20 families. Specifically, the floristic composition of Lokame forest for both banks is characterized by 21 out of 25 identified species that are common to both zones. The observation of the total number of species identified in the Table 2 shows a difference of 2 species from both sides between the left bank and the right bank. This small difference might be justified by the fact that there is proximity of the primary forest

and the relatively low degradation of the environment in this area. Meanwhile, there is no difference between the number of species of grasses and lianas along with the number of shrubs and trees between the two regions. The percentage of floristic coincidence is very high nearly of 91%. The chi-square test is no longer necessary in view of this high figure, so it is necessary to confirm the floristic similarity between the left bank and the right bank of Lokame forest. The distribution of species identified per their biological types is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of the number of species identified by biological types

Life form	Left bank		Right bank		Study area	
	No of species	Total	No of species	Total	No of species	Total
Trees	14	387	15	236	16	623
Shrubs	2	48	1	7	2	55
Lianas	4	43	4	37	4	80
Herbs	3	106	3	50	3	156
Total	23	584	23	330	25	914

Among the trees the most represented in the study area, the high density of *Triplochiton scleroxylon* is noted with 35 stems/ha, followed by *Musanga cecropioides* with 31.5 stems/ha and *Fagara spp* with 30.5 stems/ha. It should be noted that *Entandrophragma cylindricum* is less dense than the others. The presence of higher densities of *Musanga cecropioides* on the right bank than on the left bank indicates the disturbance recorded in this part of Lokame forest due to intense human activities. This density is well presented in the figure 2 below.

Cameroon. An analysis of each plant type shows that this trend is well respected for inventoried trees and lianas. On the other hand, the analysis of shrubs shows that aphrodisiacs prevail over food and miscellaneous services. As for herbs, the analysis shows that their use is exclusively reserved for miscellaneous services (64.1%) and food (35.89%). The particularity of trees lies in the fact that the proportions of the other uses are not negligible and this suggests that trees are the most versatile plant species in Lokame forest area. These figures confirm previous studies [1, 18-20].

Figure 2. Density of related species found at Lokame Forest
 Plant species found in Lokame forest are mainly used as food sources, medicinal plants, aphrodisiacs and in various services. The proportions are gradually decreasing from the left bank to the right bank. It should be noted that the medicinal use of Lokame forest products less (8.862%) in the entire study area because of Loko Hospital located at less than one kilometer of the forest. And this justifies the high rate of medicinal and aphrodisiac use on the left bank of the forest compared to the right bank. Food use is the main use of NTFP in this forest, i.e. 39.38% of all inventoried species, followed by various services (38.29%), aphrodisiac (13.45) and medicinal plants (8.86%). This corroborates with [1] who reported that the floral cortege of garden box is composed mostly of food species. According to [1], food use comes in third place (28.39%) after therapeutic use (66.41%) and miscellaneous services (32.29%) in the rainforest of

Figure 3. Proportion of different organs used per site and around the study area

Figure 4. Frequency of NTFP collection techniques practiced in the study area

Table 3. Report on the use of Non-Timber Forest Products

Usage	Trees		Shrubs		Lianas		Herbs		Total	
	Species	%	Species	%	Species	%	Species	%	Species	%
Food	236	37.88	20	36.36	48	60	56	35.89	360	39.38
Medicinal	61	9.79	-	-	20	25	-	-	81	8.86
Miscellaneous services	234	37.56	4	7.27	12	15	100	64.10	350	38.29
Aphrodisiacs	92	14.76	31	56.36	-	-	-	-	123	13.45
Total	623	100	55	100	80	100	156	100	914	100

All plant organs are used in the forest area of Lokame. The majority of the peasants surveyed think all plant organs of Lokame forest are used and the choice of the organ depends on the product to be harvested, the local knowledge and their uses. From both banks, the fruit is the most used organ (75%) followed by the bark (60%) and the leaves (50%) because a large proportion of useful plants in this forest are fruit trees that are often conserved. However, the fruit harvest in most cases does not pose any problem to the vegetative organ of the tree. As regards to bark, roots stem and wood, their proportions, although small in relation to those of fruits and leaves, are disturbing because their exploitation can lead to the death of the tree.

The figure 3 displays the proportions of the different organs used per site and throughout the study area.

As for the techniques of NTFP collection, they vary according to the organs used. They range from picking up to the cutting down of the plant through the debarking, thinning out, collection and uprooting. The percentage of these different techniques is given in figure 4.

It is observed that, debarking is the most important collection technique in this area with a frequency of 70%. The debarking is followed by the cutting down, picking-up, collection, thinning out and uprooting. The fact that the harvest by cutting down the trees is very frequent compared to the collection proves that the fruit trees in the forest area of Lokame are not conserved. Although, thinning out and uprooting is in small proportions, they still remain destructive techniques.

The results of the present study showed that Lokame forest has a vertical structure composed of three strata according to biological types and NTFP-producing species are recruited among these different biological types. However, [21] reported that the general structure of the African dense forest is characterized by a great diversity and biological richness of the stands, one of which dominates the gigantism of trees whose height can exceed 40 meters. Thus, five strata are distinguished, namely: superior tree stratum, middle tree stratum, lower tree stratum, shrub stratum and herbaceous stratum. According to [22], the virgin stand is divided into dominated species (20 to 100 cm), intermediate species (100 to 180 cm), under dominated species (180 to 260 cm) and dominant species (larger than 260 cm).

Regardless of the region, food is the major use of NTFPs in the area of Lokame forest with 39% of the study area and fruit is the most used organ (75%). According to [20], the best-known NTFPs are used as feed, fodder, medicinal plants and building materials while the edible parts of plants (fruits, nuts, leaves, vegetables, condiments and beverages) are the most important NTFPs provided. However, [11] has shown that plants provide many products used for food and these products include fruits that the pulp can be eaten raw or cooked, fruits with oilseed having seeds that are consumed either boiled or roasted, roasted seeds and almonds, vegetable leaves eaten most often cooked, tuber stems in form of whole or peeled aerial axes, sap, etc. These wild edible

fruits are essential for a balanced diet especially in children because of their richness in vitamin C and mineral salts.

After analyzing the proportions of the organs used and the collection techniques as shown in figures 3 and 4, it remains to be seen whether the organs used and the collection techniques are made in such a way as to ensure the production in a sustainable manner.

Author [18] reported that the collection of leaves reduce or prevent photosynthetic capacities of a tree. The exploitation of stems leads to the disappearance of the individual if the species does not have the emission capacities of discharges (case of *Triplochiton scleroxylon*). The use of saps and exudates is generally safe, according to these authors, although the injuries left by the tools may constitute the point of entry for certain parasites.

For the present work, the results show that the collection techniques of NTFPs practiced in Lokame forest pose a number of problems. First, fruit collection techniques are not entirely sustainable because it is necessary for collectors to always use a pole in order to selectively gauge only the ripe fruits but as it is the case for plantations, some collectors knowingly kill the entire tree. Thus, [23] reported that it is virtually impossible to remove anything from natural forests without creating noticeable change. While, [24] believe that a more pragmatic approach to the sustainable collection of NTFPs could require no loss of species and no irreversible change in the ecosystem process.

Secondly, the collection by debarking, uprooting and cutting down is really destructive and therefore not sustainable. However, debarked or uprooted trees may lose their vigor and can lead to the devitalization and death of the plant. Moreover, the wounds left by the collection can constitute potential sites of attack of pests and diseases. The proportions of NTFPs collection are alarming for the conservation of the forest area of Lokame.

CONCLUSION

Data collected over a total area of 2 ha allowed the identification of 914 plant species belonging to 20 families and 25 different plant species are producing non-timber forest products, of which 39% are food, 38% for miscellaneous services, 14% as aphrodisiacs and 9% are used as medicinal plants and fruit is the most used organ (75%). Debarking was the most important collection technique for the entire study area with a frequency of 70%. The debarking is followed by cutting down, picking-up, collection, thinning-out and uprooting.

Collection by debarking, uprooting and cutting-down is destructive, and therefore it is not sustainable. The proportions of NTFPs collection are alarming for the conservation of the forest area of Lokame. Therefore, it is necessary: (1) to strengthen knowledge on NTFPs and sustainable management techniques associated with their exploitation, (2) to develop and implement the NTFP sector specific institutional and regulatory framework, (3) to realize the economic diagnostic and master the traceability of NTFP sector (4) to strengthen institutional and human capacities for the development of NTFP sector and (5) to create a

conducive environment to invest in NTFP sector. Thus, Lokame natural forest will continue to play its role of conserving biodiversity and sustained production of natural resources.

REFERENCES

1. Y.N. Mekembom. Contribution à l'étude du potentiel en produits forestiers non ligneux et fruitiers conventionnels des agroforêts à base de cacaoyer de la zone forestière humide au Cameroun : Cas des régions d'Okola, Mfou et Ebolowa. Mémoire de DEA, Université de Deschang, Cameroun. 118p, 2005.
2. K.N. Ngbolua, G.M. Ngemale., N.F. Konzi, C.A. Masengo, Z.B. Gbolo, B.M. Bangata., T.S. Yangba, N. Gbiangbada. Utilisation de produits forestiers non ligneux à Gbadolite (District du Nord-Ubangi, Province de l'Equateur, R.D. Congo): Cas de Cola acuminata (P.Beauv.) Schott & Endl. (Malvaceae) et de Piper guineense Schumach. & Thonn. (Piperaceae). Congo Sciences 2 (2) : 61-66, 2014.
3. J.A. Asimonyio, K. Kambale, E. Shutsha, G.N. Bongo, D.S.T. Tshibangu, P.T. Mpiana, K.N. Ngbolua. Phytoecological Study of Uma Forest (Kisangani City, Democratic Republic Of The Congo). J. of Advanced Botany and Zoology, V3I2. DOI: 10.15297/JABZ.V3I2.01, 2015.
4. J.A. Asimonyio, J.C. Ngabu, C.B. Lomba, C.M. Falanga, P.T. Mpiana, K.N. Ngbolua. Structure et diversité d'un peuplement forestier hétérogène dans le bloc sud de la réserve forestière de Yoko (Ubundu, République Démocratique du Congo). International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research 18 (2): 241-251, 2015.
5. B.G. Badjedjea, B.J. Akuboy, M.F. Masudi, J.A. Asimonyio, K.P. Museu, K.N. Ngbolua. A preliminary survey of the amphibian fauna of Kisangani eco-region, Democratic Republic of the Congo. J. of Advanced Botany and Zoology, V3I4. DOI: 10.15297/JABZ.V3I4.01, 2015.
6. P. Baelo, C. Kahandi, J. Akuboyi1, J.L. Juakaly, K.N. Ngbolua. Contribution à l'étude de la biodiversité et de l'écologie des Araignées du sol dans un champ cultivé de Manihot esculenta Crantz (Euphorbiaceae) à Kisangani, RD Congo. International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research 23 (2): 412-418, 2016.
7. J.K. Kambale, F.M. Feza, J.M. Tsongo, J.A. Asimonyio, S. Mapeta, H. Nshimba, B.Z. Gbolo, P.T. Mpiana, K.N. Ngbolua. La filière bois-énergie et dégradation des écosystèmes forestiers en milieu périurbain: Enjeux et incidence sur les riverains de l'île Mbiye à Kisangani (République Démocratique du Congo). International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research 21 (1): 51-60, 2016.
8. J.-L.K. Kambale, J.A. Asimonyio, R.E. Shutsha, E.W. Katembo, J.M. Tsongo, P.K. Kavira, E.I. Yokana, K.K. Bukasa, H.S. Nshimba, P.T. Mpiana, K.N. Ngbolua. Etudes floristique et structurale des forêts dans le domaine de chasse de Rubi-Télé (Province de Bas-Uélé, République Démocratique du Congo). International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research 24 (2): 309-321, 2016.
9. J.-L.K. Kambale, R.E. Shutsha, E.W. Katembo, J.M. Omatoko, F.B. Kirongozi, O.D. Basa, E.P. Bugentho, E.I. Yokana, K.K. Bukasa, H.S. Nshimba, K.N. Ngbolua. Etude floristique et structurale de deux groupements végétaux mixtes sur terre hydromorphe et ferme de la forêt de Kponyo (Province du Bas-Uélé, R.D. Congo). International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research 24 (2): 300-308, 2016.
10. P.K. Kavira, F.B. Kirongozi, J.-L.K. Kambale, J.M. Tsongo, N.A. Shalufa, K.K. Bukasa, P.Y. Sabongo, H.K. Nzapu, K.N. Ngbolua. Caractéristiques de la régénération naturelle du sous-bois forestier du Jardin botanique S. Lisowski (Kisangani, République Démocratique du Congo). International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research 24 (2): 322-331, 2016.
11. C. Termote. Wild edible plants use in Tshopo District, Democratic Republic of Congo. PhD Thesis, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, University of Ghent, Belgium, 2012.
12. Code forestier. Loi N°02/2002 du 29/08/2002 portant code forestier de la République démocratique du Congo, Journal officiel du MECNT, 39p, 2002.
13. SPIAF. Normes d'inventaire forestier. Guide opérationnel. MECNT, 33p, 2007.
14. B. Tuka. Notes de Climatologie, IFA Yangambi, Kisangani. 104p, 2008.
15. A.Z. Bau. Effet de différenciation d'amendement organique sur le rendement de légume-feuille. Cas d'amarante à Gbadolite. Travail de Fin de cycle. Université de Gbadolite, République démocratique du Congo, 32p, 2014.
16. Agripel, 2014. Rapport annuel de l'inspection urbaine de l'Agriculture, Pêche et Elevage. Gbadolite. 45p.
17. A. Hladick, Jr.E.G. Leigh, F. Bourlière. Disponibilités des ressources alimentaires dans les forêts tropicales: contexte et données récentes. In Hladick C.M, Hladick A., Pagezy H., Linares F.O, Koppert J.A. et Froment A., l'Alimentation en forêt tropicale. Interactions bioculturelles et perspectives de développement, pp. 219-260, 1996.
18. M. Tchatat. Les jardins de case agroforestiers des basses terres humides du Cameroun : Etude de cas des zones forestières des provinces du Centre et Sud. Thèse de doctorat, Université de Paris 6, 145p, 1996.
19. J.F.W. Van Dijk. Non-timber forest products in the Bipindi-Akom II region, Cameroon: a socio-economic and ecological assessment. Tropenbos-Cameroon Programme, Kribi, Cameroon. 197p, 1999.
20. D.J. Sonwa. Biomass management and diversification within cocoa agroforests in the humid forest zone of southern Cameroon. Thèse de doctorat, Kumba, Cameroun, 130p, 2004.
21. D. Lokombe. Notes de cours de Sylviculture et Agroforesterie, 3e graduat, ISEA Bengamisa, République démocratique du Congo, 69p, 2010.
22. R. Pierlot. Sylviculture tropicale. Traité des caractéristiques des forêts denses africaines. Brazzaville, Congo. 56p, 1966.
23. J.L.G. Wong, K. Thornber, N. Baker. Evaluation des ressources en produits forestiers non ligneux: expérience et principes de dendrométrie. Produits forestiers non ligneux 13. FAO. Rome, 2001.
24. R.G.A. Boot & R.E. Gullison R.E., 1995. Approaches to developing sustainable extraction systems for tropical forest products. Ecol. Appl. 5(4): 896-903, 1995.

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